

Reactions of Benzyl Alcohol over Copper Chromite

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Manuscript received 27 February 1995, revised 19 July 1995, accepted 27 August 1995

Benzyl alcohol undergoes disproportionation reaction over alumina to give toluene and benzaldehyde¹. Benzyl alcohol undergoes different reactions over acid catalysts, both homogeneous² and heterogeneous³. On dehydration over alumina it yields dibenzyl ether⁴. Formation of anthracene from benzyl alcohol over alumina and zeolites is reported^{4,5}.

Copper chromite is an excellent catalyst for different reactions, like reductive alkylation of amines⁶⁻⁹, hydrogenation¹⁰ and dehydrogenation of diol¹¹. Since benzylalcohol undergoes different reactions over oxide catalysts, it was thought worthwhile to investigate reactions of benzyl alcohol over copper chromite. The behaviour of certain aliphatic alcohols over copper chromite have been reported^{8,11}. This work aims at studying the reactions of benzyl alcohol in vapour phase over copper chromite catalyst.

Results and Discussion

Reactions of benzyl alcohol over copper chromite was studied at 250–450° in a fixed bed flow-type reactor under atmospheric pressure in vapour phase. Benzyl alcohol without diluent was admitted in the reactor using a syringe pump at a predetermined flow rate. Benzyl alcohol on disproportionation reaction over copper chromite produced toluene, benzaldehyde and water,

The reaction over alumina has been shown to involve a hydride transfer from a surface benzyl oxide mostly to the positively polarised α -carbon of a neighbouring benzyloxy species. Scheme 1 is an adaptation from an earlier report⁵.

Scheme 1

It was observed that the molar ratio of the yield of toluene and benzaldehyde was not 1 : 1. The mole % yield of benzaldehyde was more than that of toluene. If there was only disproportionation reaction mole % yield of toluene and benzaldehyde would have been equal. Since the yield

of benzaldehyde is higher than that of toluene, it clearly indicates that dehydrogenation of benzyl alcohol had taken place over the catalyst. Dehydrogenation of 1,4-butanediol over copper chromite to succinaldehyde is reported¹¹.

Reactions were carried out at different temperatures (250, 300, 350, 400 and 450°) and the results are given in Table 1. As expected the conversion of benzyl alcohol in-

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND FLOW RATE

Weight of catalyst = 5 g

Temp. °C	Flow rate ml h ⁻¹	Mole % conversion of benzyl alcohol	Products (% Selectivity)	
			Toluene	Benzaldehyde
250	10	38.3	36.3	63.7
300	10	51.0	34.0	66.0
350	10	73.1	31.4	68.6
400	10	75.6	29.2	70.8
450	10	78.2	26.6	72.4
350	20	52.5	33.0	67.0
350	30	36.2	36.3	63.7
350	40	27.0	38.8	61.2

increased with the increase in temperature. The selectivity towards benzaldehyde increased with increasing temperature. The observation is the same as that reported on study of benzyl alcohol over zeolites⁵. Experiments were also performed at different flow rates (10, 20, 30 and 40 ml h⁻¹) and the results are given in Table 1. The mole % conversion of benzyl alcohol decreased with the increase in flow rate. The selectivity towards toluene increased with increasing flow rate (decrease in contact time). As in the case of alumina and zeolites, the formation of dibenzyl ether or the formation of anthracene was not observed over copper chromite. This may be attributed to the less acidic nature of copper chromite compared to the oxide catalysts like alumina and zeolites.

The rapid deactivation of copper chromite catalyst used for reductive alkylation of aniline with acetone⁷, reductive alkylation of ethanolamine with benzaldehyde⁶ and dehydrogenation of 1,4-butanediol¹¹ has been reported earlier. Based on these studies, it was decided to investigate the activity of the catalyst on prolonged use in the present investigation. The reaction was performed continuously for 7 h (Table 2). The mole % conversion of benzyl alcohol in the first hour was 73.4 which gradually decreased to 57.3 at the 7th hour. The surface area of the used catalyst decreased (fresh catalyst 59, used catalyst 29 m²g⁻¹). The thermogravimetric analysis showed 11.8% weight-loss in the used

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TABLE 2 - STUDY OF TIME ON STREAM OF REACTION OF BENZYL ALCOHOL OVER COPPER CHROMITE

Weight of catalyst = 5g, flow rate = 10 ml h⁻¹
Temp. = 350°

Time on stream h	Mole % conversion	Product (% Selectivity)	
		Toluene	Benzaldehyde
1	73.4	31.0	69.0
2	69.4	29.5	70.5
3	66.1	27.7	72.3
4	64.9	25.9	74.1
5	62.8	24.0	76.0
6	60.3	22.8	77.2
7	57.3	21.0	79.0
Regenerated	66.8	32.0	68.0

catalyst. The pore volume of the used catalyst was reduced by 10.5%. The pore volume of the fresh catalyst was 0.19 and that of used catalyst was 0.13 ml g⁻¹. The surface area and pore volume loss of the catalyst is attributed to the blocking of pores and covering of surface by organic molecules. The used catalyst was burnt in a current of air at 500° and carbon dioxide evolved was absorbed in barium hydroxide solution. The weight of carbon was determined from barium carbonate formed. It is evident that the coverage of the surface of the catalyst and the blockage of pores of catalyst were due to carbonaceous material. Hence, the loss in activity is because of covering of active sites of the catalyst by carbonaceous material formed during the process.

The deactivated catalyst was regenerated by heating in a current of air at 450° for 6 h. The activity of the regenerated catalyst was improved (66.8). But the activity of the regenerated catalyst was slightly less than that of the fresh catalyst. It can be concluded that, benzyl alcohol on copper chromite disproportionates to give toluene, benzaldehyde and water, and on dehydrogenation benzaldehyde and hydrogen are produced. High temperature favours dehydrogenation reaction rather than disproportionation of benzyl alcohol over copper chromite.

Experimental

Commercial copper chromite catalyst was used

(Harshaw Cu 1955, surface area 59 m² g⁻¹, bulk density 1.6 g ml⁻¹, CuO : 45 wt %, Cr₂O₃ : 45 wt %; pore volume 0.19, average particle size 20 microns). Copper chromite (5 g) in powder form was taken in a pyrex glass reactor (2.5 cm dia × 40 cm) kept in cylindrical ceramic furnace. The catalyst was activated by heating in a current of dry air at 400° for 4 h. The benzyl alcohol was introduced to the reactor by a syringe pump. Quantitative yields of the condensed products were determined by gas chromatograph using 10% methyl silicone column (5 m length, flame ionisation detector). The products were characterised by chemical analysis as well as by their ir, pmr and mass spectra. The gas product was collected by downward displacement of water in a graduated tube.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Prof. V. G. Kumar Das, Prof. C. C. Ho of University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur and Prof. C. N. Pillai of I.I.T., Madras for valuable discussions.

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